

REGARDING THE STUDY OF VARIATIONS IN THE LEGEND GENRE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13304462>

Abstract: This article presents theoretical approaches to narrative analysis, as well as specific examples of research based on comparative analysis of texts, historical context, and cultural heritage. The diversity of approaches to the study of legendary stories allows a deep understanding of their role in the formation of cultural identity and collective consciousness

Keywords: Myth, folklore, cultural heritage, textual analysis, historical context, comparative study, cultural identity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Legends and myths, which are the product of people's thinking and creativity, mainly originate from specific historical conditions and events. These legends and myths, which reflect life's hardships and dreams, have always interpreted a unique struggle between goodness and evil, black and white, good and evil. From the point of view of this generation, in this case, today's young people are supporting these two technologies in their mind and thinking. Because as our head of state said: "The reality of life in this world is to see that any progress can be made for two different purposes - the path of goodness and evil" [1].

Legend is one of the oldest genres of Uzbek folklore. Legend is derived from the Persian word "afsun" and means prose stories based on fiction, magic, and life fiction. Such stories are expressed by the word caw in Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu lug'otit turk" and it is interpreted as a story. Myths, compelling stories woven into the fabric of cultures, are not static entities [3]. They change, evolve and adapt over time and space, reflecting the dynamic nature of the human story. Exploring the diversity of myths explores this rich tapestry of stories, threads of cultural heritage, historical change, and human imagination.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Myths, often based on historical events or mythological motifs, serve as a means of transmitting cultural values, beliefs, and customs to generations. However, no two iterations of the legend are the same. Each variation contains nuances shaped by geographic location, social context, and individual storytellers. Studying these changes provides insight into the complexities of human interaction, communication, and interpretation.

Researchers use different methodologies to study changes in Legends. Comparative analysis, a basic approach, involves juxtaposing different versions of a myth to identify common themes, motifs, and deviations. Historical analysis places narratives in a specific temporal context, traces their development over

time and their interaction with socio-political dynamics. Linguistic and narratological analysis examines the structural elements of narratives in depth, examines modes of narration, linguistic features, and stylistic changes.

Arthurian Legends: Tales of King Arthur and the Knights of the Round Table proliferated throughout medieval Europe, with each version adding new characters, plot twists, and moral dilemmas. Comparative studies reveal how these differences reflect the cultural aspirations, political ideologies, and literary trends of different periods.

The Legend of Robin Hood: From medieval ballads to Hollywood blockbusters, the legend of Robin Hood has undergone countless variations. Analyzing these changes reveals the changing perceptions of heroism, justice, and rebellion over the centuries.

Urban Legends: In the digital age, urban legends have spread virally through social media, mutating rapidly as they traverse virtual networks. Examining these contemporary myths illuminates the role of technology in the dissemination of folklore and the blurred boundaries between fact and fiction.

Legends denaturalize events and images, but the subject is short and non-moving. So, there is no subject and composition in legends. It depends on the form of social performance and the use of information. According to the subject of legends, conventionally pure mythological legends are divided into legends woven about historical events and events [2]. Such a characteristic is evident in the fact that the subject is built on the basis of fantastic fictions and plays an excellent decisive role in the resolution of the conflict. Legends of this type tell the story of blind earth and sky gods, supernatural actions of mermen, and the appearance of people in fantastical images or fairy tales. In fact, there are also interpretations related to the religion of fire worship in the episodes of many legends. Mythological legends such as "Qayumars", "Odami Od", "Er Hubbi", "Anbar ona", "Hazrati Khizr" are at

the root of the primitive worldview, the sanctification of this or that mysterious thing, and the belief in it appeared [5]. We mainly refer to legends in written sources. For this purpose, we will connect them with one or another written literature. However, they entered the written sources from the oral creation of the people.

Therefore, they can be considered as belonging to the oral creation of the people at the same time. If you remember that the legends are embedded in the life of the people, they are the basis of some rituals and customs, this becomes even stronger. Examples of mythological legends remain in historical works, religious books and memoirs. One of the earlier legends in Beruni's works is "Qayumars". It arose as a result of the myth about the emergence of man [4]. Because mythological heroes were considered sacred in primitive times and became spiritual helpers of the people. This ideological mission is largely forgotten in this legend, and it has turned into a simple religious story.

Future research could explore interdisciplinary approaches, incorporate digital humanities methodologies, and engage local perspectives to enrich our understanding of mythic change in a globalized world. Exploring the diversity of myths is like embarking on a journey through the collective imagination of mankind. Each variation reveals a new layer of meaning that reveals insights into the diverse tapestry of human cultures, histories, and identities. Uncovering the nuances of the diversity of myths, scholars illuminate the timeless appeal of storytelling and the enduring power of myth and legend to shape our understanding of the world.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Legends often tell a story in connection with a religious event or object. This thing originated from the purpose of convincing people of a myth. because of this, many people consider the events reflected in the legend to be true. Since there is no tradition in the subject of legends, the structure of the subject is not complicated. For this, the subject is always changing due to the skill of the speaker. The subject of the legend consists of mythological events, strange events related to the names of geographical places. Character control, the plot of all legends consists of one or two episodes. The events of the subject mostly start from birth. And such epic knots lead listeners to unexpected events.

So, the myth is an epic genre with an informational task, and it is of great scientific importance as a rare source for the study of the origin of the people, the emergence of the name of this or that place, as well as events in society and nature..

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